

Seven Versus Fourteen Days for Resistant Bloodstream Infections:

What Do We Actually Know?

A Scoping Review — Pre-specified Internal Protocol

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1. Registration and protocol transparency

This protocol was not prospectively registered in a public registry before the search. PROSPERO (the international prospective register of systematic reviews maintained by NIHR/CRD) **does not accept scoping review protocols** and, at the time this review was conducted, no equivalent mandatory registry existed for this study design. We therefore adopted the following transparency procedure in line with PRISMA-ScR (Tricco et al., *Ann Intern Med* 2018), item 5, which requires: “*explicit details on how to access the protocol, including information on how to obtain a protocol that is not publicly available.*”

- The full content of this protocol — research question, eligibility criteria, search string, and evidence-charting categories — was finalized on **15 January 2026**, i.e., 31 days before the PubMed search was executed on 15 February 2026.
- No element of this protocol was modified during the conduct of the review. Any deviation from this protocol in the final manuscript is to be regarded as an unintended post-hoc deviation and should be disclosed in the manuscript's Limitations section.
- After completion of the review, this protocol has been deposited in Zenodo (CERN repository) with the permanent Digital Object Identifier 10.5281/zenodo.19641610. The DOI is cited in the Methods section of the published manuscript. Readers who require direct access can also obtain the protocol from the corresponding author upon request.
- The data-charting form (spreadsheet of all references handled during the review) has been deposited in the same Zenodo record (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.19641610) for full reproducibility.

2. Background and rationale

The traditional 10–14 day course of antibiotics for bloodstream infections (BSI) has rested for decades on convention rather than evidence (Havey et al., *Crit Care* 2011). Four landmark randomized controlled trials — Yahav et al. (2019), von Dach et al. (2020), Molina et al. (2022), and the BALANCE trial (2025) — have collectively established that 7 days of antibiotic therapy is noninferior to 14 days for BSI, and their results have been consolidated in six independent meta-analyses (Lee et al. 2025; Luna et al. 2026; Zhao et al. 2025; Prager et al. 2025; Liu et al. 2025; Turjeman et al. 2022). The question of duration for susceptible Gram-negative BSI can reasonably be considered settled.

What has not been settled is whether these findings extend to **resistant organisms**. Although three of the four definitive RCTs reported the prevalence of MDR organisms (Yahav: 17.9% MDR; von Dach: 5.0% ESBL; Molina: 16.6% ESBL/AmpC), none but Yahav et al. performed resistance-stratified outcome analyses. MRSA bacteremia was explicitly excluded. ESBL producers, carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (CPE), vancomycin-resistant enterococci (VRE), and MDR non-fermenters were either absent or present in unknown proportions across the definitive trials. The only RCT specifically designed for MDR Gram-negative BSI — the OPTIMISE trial — was halted in 2024 after enrolling only 103 of 382 planned patients.

A parallel body of observational literature has explored shorter courses in broader populations, with a small number of studies specifically targeting resistant BSI (e.g., Le Berre et al. 2025 for ESBL-E; Soto et al. 2024 for CRE; Bahrs et al. 2023 and Torres et al. 2025 for VRE). None of these studies, however, were powered to establish noninferiority.

Rationale for a scoping review over a systematic review. Our objective is not to synthesize effect estimates across the available evidence — which would be premature given the paucity and heterogeneity of resistance-stratified data — but to **map systematically what evidence exists, and what does not**, on antibiotic duration for BSI across five distinct resistance categories. This is precisely the indication for which Munn et al. (*BMC Med Res Methodol* 2018) recommend a scoping review rather than a systematic review.

3. Review objectives and research question

Primary objective. To map the available evidence on antibiotic duration for BSI, stratified by resistance mechanism, and to identify the gaps that must be addressed before shorter courses can be recommended for resistant infections.

Research question (PCC framework). The research question was formulated a priori using the Population–Concept–Context framework recommended by the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis for scoping reviews:

Element	Definition adopted in this review
Population (P)	Adult patients (≥ 18 years) with documented bloodstream infection (BSI) caused by antimicrobial-resistant organisms, defined a priori across five pre-specified resistance categories (§7).
Concept (C)	Optimal antibiotic duration (shorter — typically ≤ 7 –10 days — vs longer courses — typically 14–21 days).
Context (C)	Hospital settings, including general wards and intensive care units; community- and hospital-acquired BSI; worldwide.

Final research question. “What evidence is available on optimal antibiotic duration (Concept) for BSI caused by antimicrobial-resistant organisms (Population) in hospital settings (Context)?”

4. Methodological framework and reporting standard

- **Methodological framework:** Arksey H, O’Malley L. *Int J Soc Res Methodol* 2005;8(1):19–32, as refined by Levac et al. *Implement Sci* 2010;5:69.
- **Reporting standard:** PRISMA-ScR checklist — Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. *Ann Intern Med* 2018;169(7):467–473. The full item-by-item compliance is reported in the companion document *PRISMA-ScR_Checklist_Completed.pdf* deposited in Zenodo.
- **Equator Network:** This protocol was developed consulting the broader catalogue of reporting guidelines curated by the EQUATOR Network (<https://www.equator-network.org>).

5. Eligibility criteria

5.1 Inclusion criteria

- **Study design:** (i) Randomized controlled trials comparing antibiotic durations for BSI in adults; (ii) meta-analyses of such RCTs; (iii) observational studies reporting duration-related outcomes for Gram-negative or Gram-positive BSI using methods to adjust for confounding (propensity score matching, IPTW, target trial emulation, cloning approach, multivariate adjustment).
- **Population:** Adults (≥ 18 years) with culture-confirmed BSI.
- **Intervention / Comparator:** Any defined shorter-course antibiotic regimen compared to any defined longer-course antibiotic regimen, where the minimum difference between the two arms/groups is ≥ 3 days.
- **Outcomes:** Any clinical outcome reported by the primary study (mortality at any time point, clinical failure, microbiological failure, relapse, recurrence, emergence of resistance, length of hospital stay, adverse events).
- **Language:** English.
- **Date range:** No lower date limit; upper limit defined by the PubMed search date (15 February 2026).

5.2 Exclusion criteria

- Paediatric-only studies (population < 18 years entirely).
- Studies of antibiotic **choice** (e.g., one drug vs another) rather than antibiotic **duration**.
- Studies of non-BSI infections without a dedicated bacteremia subgroup analysis.
- Case reports, case series with $n < 10$, narrative reviews, editorials, commentaries, and conference abstracts without subsequent full-text publication.
- Duplicate/overlapping cohorts: when multiple publications report on the same cohort, the most recent and/or largest is retained.
- Non-English publications.

6. Information sources and literature search

6.1 Primary database

PubMed/MEDLINE. Single-database searching was adopted a priori because the objective of a scoping review is mapping rather than pooled estimation; PubMed/MEDLINE provides adequate coverage of the clinical infectious-diseases literature relevant to the research question. The use of a single database is acknowledged as a limitation in the manuscript.

6.2 Search string

The following PubMed search string was pre-specified and executed on 15 February 2026, without modification:

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("bloodstream infection" OR "bacteremia" OR "bacteraemia") AND
("antibiotic duration" OR "duration of therapy" OR "treatment duration" OR
"short course" OR "7 days" OR "14 days" OR "shorter") AND ("gram-negative"
OR "Enterobacteriaceae" OR "Enterobacterales" OR "resistance" OR "ESBL" OR
"carbapenemase" OR "MRSA" OR "VRE" OR "multidrug-resistant")
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6.3 Supplementary search

- Hand-searching of reference lists of all included studies, meta-analyses, and contemporary guidelines (notably IDSA 2024 guidance on antimicrobial-resistant Gram-negative infections).
- Cross-checking with the authors' pre-existing bibliographic databases and with the reference lists of the six identified meta-analyses.
- No grey literature, no clinical trial registry harvesting, no non-English sources.

7. Evidence-charting categories

Five pre-specified resistance categories were defined before the search was executed. These categories were chosen because they correspond to the resistance phenotypes currently most relevant to clinical decision-making in BSI and most commonly addressed in contemporary guidelines.

Category	Organisms / phenotype	Rationale
ESBL-E	ESBL-producing Enterobacterales (incl. ESBL/AmpC where combined in the source study)	Most frequent resistant Gram-negative BSI phenotype worldwide; partially represented in the definitive RCTs at 5–17%.
CPE	Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (KPC, OXA-48, NDM, VIM, IMP)	High-mortality phenotype; nearly absent from the definitive RCTs; relevant to IDSA 2024 guidance.
MRSA	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> bacteremia	Explicitly excluded from all four definitive RCTs; dedicated RCT (SAB7) ongoing.
VRE	Vancomycin-resistant <i>Enterococcus faecium</i> / <i>faecalis</i> bacteremia	Limited randomized evidence; expanding observational literature.
MDR-NF	MDR non-fermenting Gram-negatives: difficult-to-treat <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , carbapenem-resistant	Highest clinical stakes; dedicated SHORTEN-2 RCT currently recruiting.

	Acinetobacter baumannii, Stenotrophomonas maltophilia	
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Data items extracted. For each included study: first author and year; country/setting; study design; sample size; population (age, comorbidities, ICU status); pathogen distribution; resistance data (proportion and phenotype); definitions of shorter and longer durations (in days); primary outcome and timing; effect estimates with 95% confidence intervals; statistical methods used to adjust for confounding.

8. Study selection process

- **Dual independent screening.** Two independent reviewers (NLM and PV) screened titles, abstracts, and full texts against the pre-specified eligibility criteria. Disagreements were resolved by discussion with a third reviewer (VZ or EA).
- **Software.** Screening performed in a shared spreadsheet (data-charting form). No specific screening software was used.
- **Reporting of the selection process.** Reported in a PRISMA-ScR flow diagram (Figure 1 of the manuscript), which reports: records identified from PubMed, records identified by hand-search, duplicates removed, records screened, records excluded at title/abstract stage, full-text reports assessed, full-text reports excluded with reasons, and final number of studies included.

9. Synthesis and analysis

- **No risk-of-bias assessment.** Consistent with scoping review methodology (Arksey & O'Malley 2005; Levac et al. 2010; Munn et al. 2018), no formal risk-of-bias appraisal of individual studies was performed.
- **No meta-analytic synthesis.** No pooling of effect estimates was performed. Evidence is presented narratively and tabulated by resistance category.
- **Evidence map.** Evidence is mapped by resistance category (§7) in a dedicated table (Table 4 of the manuscript) reporting, for each category: available randomized evidence, available observational evidence, ongoing RCTs, and key evidence gaps.
- **Hierarchical presentation.** Within each resistance category, randomized evidence is presented first and observational evidence second. The study design of every cited study is stated explicitly to prevent unintended equivalence between randomized and non-randomized evidence.

10. Deviations from protocol

To be documented in the manuscript's Limitations section if any deviation from this protocol occurs during the conduct of the review. As of the finalization date of this protocol, no deviation is anticipated.

11. Ethics and data availability

- This scoping review is based exclusively on published, peer-reviewed data. No ethical approval is required.

- This protocol and the data-charting form are deposited in Zenodo with a permanent identifier, accessible to any reader.

12. Funding and conflicts of interest

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13. Amendments

This is version 1.0, finalized on 15 January 2026. Any subsequent amendment would be posted as a new version in the same Zenodo record (as a new version), with a dated change-log.

14. Key references

Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *Int J Soc Res Methodol.* 2005;8(1):19–32.

Levac D, Colquhoun H, O'Brien KK. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology. *Implement Sci.* 2010;5:69.

Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): checklist and explanation. *Ann Intern Med.* 2018;169(7):467–473.

Munn Z, Peters MDJ, Stern C, et al. Systematic review or scoping review? Guidance for authors. *BMC Med Res Methodol.* 2018;18(1):143.

Peters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, et al. Best practice guidance and reporting items for the development of scoping review protocols. *JB Evid Synth.* 2022;20(4):953–968.